

RECONSTRUCTION OF EQUITABLE FIDUCIARY SECURITY

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the condition that in Various cases that have occurred show that fiduciary execution is often carried out in inhumane ways and is contrary to the principles of justice. This study aims to answer questions regarding the nature of Fiduciary guarantees, the implementation of Fiduciary guarantees before and after the Constitutional Court decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019, and the reconstruction of fair Fiduciary guarantee law. This research is a normative-empirical legal research using a statutory approach, normative approach, conceptual approach, historical approach, comparative approach, sociological approach and philosophical approach. The results of the study indicate that, The essence of fiduciary guarantees in the Indonesian legal system is a form of material guarantee based on the principle of trust, where the fiduciary giver remains in physical control of the collateral object, while the ownership rights are legally transferred to the fiduciary recipient. The implementation of the execution of fiduciary guarantees before the Constitutional Court Decision No. 18 / PUU-XVII / 2019 took place unilaterally by the creditor through the parate execution mechanism based on Article 15 of Law No. 42 of 1999, the Constitutional Court Decision corrected this practice and required an agreement on default and voluntary surrender, or an application to the court, as a valid condition for the execution. A just model of reconstruction of fiduciary guarantee law must be built by balancing legal protection for debtors and creditors. The recommendations include: The government and law-making bodies need to strengthen the conceptual understanding that fiduciary guarantees are trust-based material guarantees. The government needs to formally revise Law No. 42 of 1999 to align with the Constitutional Court's ruling. Academics, practitioners, and policymakers need to use Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019 as a starting point for building a guarantee system that is more humane, just, and aligned with constitutional values.

Keywords: Fiduciary Security, Legal Reconstruction.

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, there are both banks and non-bank financial institutions. In addition to these two well-known institutions, financing institutions, business entities that provide financing in the form of funds or capital goods, have emerged to provide development funding.

Historically, it has been seen that the fiduciary institution, in its classical form, existed as early as Roman times. In this context, the Romans used the term *fiducia cum creditore*. In this legal structure, ownership of the debtor's assets was transferred to the creditor, but was intended solely as collateral for the debt. (Widiyono, 2009)

Fiduciary guarantees arose due to the public's need for credit secured by movable objects, but they still require these objects to be used daily for work or utilized in their companies. To fulfill these requirements, it is impossible to use a pawn institution that requires the collateral to be in the form of movable objects, to be under the control of the pawn holder as stated in Article 1152 Paragraph 2 of the Civil Code concerning pawns, which requires that the authority over the pawned object must not be in the pawnbroker. (Soebroto, 1995) In Indonesia, the fiduciary institution developed through jurisprudence, before the issuance of a specific law on fiduciary rights, namely Law No. 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary. The concept of providing fiduciary

security is the transfer of ownership rights through trust over material rights. Or, in legal terms, *zakalijke zekerheid* (security right in rem). What is meant by material rights here is the right to an object that can be owned and transferred. (Purnamasari, 2014)

In Article 1 paragraph 2 of Law No. 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees, what is meant by fiduciary guarantees is guarantees for movable objects, both tangible and intangible, and immovable objects, especially buildings, which cannot be burdened with mortgage rights as referred to in Law No. 4 of 1996 concerning mortgage rights which remain in the control of the fiduciary grantor, as collateral for the repayment of certain debts, which gives the fiduciary recipient a priority position over other creditors.

Consumer financing companies are business entities that carry out financing activities for the procurement of goods based on consumer needs with an installment or periodic payment system by consumers. In a consumer financing process, there are several elements, namely: (Sembiring, 2001)

- 1) The subjects are the parties involved in the consumer financing legal relationship, namely the consumer financing company (creditor), consumer (debtor) and goods provider (supplier).
- 2) Objects are movable goods for consumer purposes that will be used for living or household needs such as televisions, refrigerators, washing machines, kitchen utensils, household furniture, motorized vehicles.
- 3) Agreement, namely the act of financing agreement made between a consumer finance company and consumers, as well as buying and selling between suppliers and consumers, this agreement is supported by documents.
- 4) The relationship between rights and obligations, namely, the consumer finance company is obliged to finance the purchase price of the goods required by the consumer and pay the supplier in cash. The consumer is obliged to pay in installments to the consumer finance company, and the supplier is obliged to deliver the goods to the consumer.
- 5) Collateral, which consists of primary collateral, principal collateral, and additional collateral. The primary collateral is the consumer's (debtor's) trust that the consumer can be trusted to pay their installments until they are completed.

Lending companies require collateral from consumers to mitigate the risk of lending to consumers. The guarantor's role is to guarantee and protect the lender in the event of legal issues. Sentosa Sembiring stated that loans will be repaid on time and according to the agreement of the parties, producers and consumers, and will receive legal protection before and after installment payments. However, in reality, what often occurs in the field when making credit payments, sometimes the loan recipient (debtor) is unable to pay the fees to the financial company (creditor), so it can be said that the loan (loan) is in default. (Sembiring, 2001)

Quoting from Rachmadi Usman's book which explains that default itself is "not fulfilling or neglecting to carry out obligations as stipulated in the agreement made between the creditor and the debtor" With the existence of various problems that occur in the field regarding default

and in order to overcome this, creditors then in order to obtain the fastest and most effective credit repayment, financing companies (creditors) sometimes use parate execution to resolve bad credit, where the execution is carried out without going through the assistance of the local court where the agreement occurred". (Usman, 1999)

Meanwhile, power of attorney agreements are regulated in the Civil Code. Debt collection regulations in PBI 23/2021 relate to credit cards. Meanwhile, POJK 35/2018 regulates debt collection by financing companies from debtors. If the debtor defaults, the financing company is obliged to conduct collection, which is any effort the financing company makes to obtain its rights over the debtor's obligation to pay installments, including executing collateral in the event of default.

If we pay attention to the security guarantee, then first of all we know that the mortgage guarantee in the Civil Code (KUHPerdara) is regulated in paragraph (2) of Article 1152 of the Civil Code for mortgages which are said to be subjects, mortgages cannot be left under the control of the debtor, so that it can be seen in the implementation of this obligation in the field, debtors often carry out parate execution. (Kamelo, 2014)

If the creditor or debtor, after determining that the contract has been violated, their responsibility is confirmed by a deed of trust, then the creditor can cancel their debt and sell the mortgage under the supervision of the creditor's authority. This is because the guarantee certificate becomes a guarantee of performance if the debtor violates their obligations as regulated in the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Protection of Guarantor Article 15 e.

Basically, the object of fiduciary guarantee is made based on an agreement made by the creditor as the fiduciary recipient and the debtor as the fiduciary provider and is stated in the financing agreement. The financing agreement must also fulfill the valid requirements of the agreement in Chapter II, Article 1320 of the Civil Code.

However, in 2019, there was a petition from justice seekers to the Constitutional Court regarding the execution of fiduciary guarantees. These justice seekers argued that the provisions of Article 15 paragraph (2) and paragraph (3) of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law, which regulates the executorial title and the implementation of the execution of this fiduciary guarantee, were in conflict with Article 28D paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution.

This is because it can give rise to arbitrary actions by the fiduciary recipient (creditor) in executing the fiduciary object, where it often happens that the fiduciary recipient has used all kinds of methods to confiscate the fiduciary object, and it is necessary to further regulate how the execution procedure can be carried out so that it is also in accordance with the mechanism for executing a court decision that has permanent legal force.

Bankruptcy must be declared by a judge or court decision. A debtor (who has debt) can only be declared bankrupt if it has been declared by a judge or court with a judge's decision. (Asikin, 2013)

Based on the request of the justice seekers, finally the Constitutional Court through Decision No. 18 / PUU-XVII / 2019 granted part and stated in essence that to carry out the execution of fiduciary guarantees must be based on 2 conditions, namely the existence of an agreement on default and the debtor voluntarily surrendering the object of the fiduciary guarantee. At the time before the issuance of the Constitutional Court Decision Number 18 / PUUXVII / 2019, the execution process against the object of the fiduciary guarantee was still based on Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 42 of 1999 concerning fiduciary guarantees Article 15 paragraphs (1), (2) and (3), where the creditor as the recipient of the fiduciary can directly carry out direct execution (parate execution) against the object of the fiduciary guarantee controlled by the debtor as the giver without going through a court decision.

Constitutional Court Decision Number 18/PUU-XVII/2019 (MK Decision) regarding articles in the Fiduciary Law, particularly regarding default and execution of fiduciary guarantees, has changed its interpretation. Settlement of default and execution disputes through the courts is considered ineffective, will spend a lot of money and time, and is not a solution to achieving justice for both debtors and creditors. Because basically, debtors and creditors should respect the agreements they have made, in this case the fiduciary guarantee agreement that is ratified into a fiduciary guarantee deed. With the issuance of the Constitutional Court decision Number 18/PUU-XVII/2019, it can certainly provide justice in the procedures for implementing the execution of fiduciary guarantee objects against debtors who commit breach of promise in the State of Indonesia. (Abdulkadir, 2015)

In this regard, several cases have occurred at non-bank financial institutions, particularly those in West Nusa Tenggara. These include the case at the Mataram branch of BFI, where BFI withdrew funds from debtors using third-party services (Profcoll). The withdrawal was carried out by BFI because the debtor was in default by being in arrears with installments for 3 times, but the debtor did not accept the actions of the finance SMS which was considered to be taking the law into their own hands and forcibly seizing the vehicle. Then the debtor mobilized the masses through one of the mass organizations in Mataram to hold a demonstration and intimidate the finance party.

Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees was enacted to address the business world's need for financing, particularly trust-based financing without the physical delivery of collateral. In practice, fiduciary guarantees are widely used in consumer financing for movable assets, such as motor vehicles, electronics, and household appliances. However, this law does not fully guarantee legal certainty and protection, particularly in the enforcement of fiduciary obligations.

At the normative level, Article 15 paragraphs (2) and (3) of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law grants creditors the title of executor as fiduciary recipient, allowing for the implementation of parate execution without a court order. On the one hand, this is intended to make it easier for creditors to guarantee the repayment of their receivables. However, in practice, the implementation of execution often gives rise to legal problems, such as violations of debtor rights, arbitrary actions by debt collectors, and a lack of judicial oversight.

Various cases in the field demonstrate that fiduciary enforcement is often carried out inhumanely and contrary to the principles of justice. Many debtors feel they are victims of forced withdrawal, even without prior summons or persuasive resolution. This raises serious questions regarding the suitability of fiduciary enforcement with the values of Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, particularly Article 28D paragraph (1) concerning the right to fair legal certainty.

This public unrest ultimately gave rise to a request for a judicial review to the Constitutional Court, which then gave birth to MK Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019. This decision emphasized that the execution of fiduciary collateral objects can no longer be carried out unilaterally, but must fulfill two main conditions: (1) there is an agreement between the parties that the debtor has defaulted, and (2) the debtor voluntarily surrenders the fiduciary collateral object to the creditor. If these two conditions are not met, then the execution must be carried out through a court order.

The ruling has important implications for fiduciary guarantee law in Indonesia. On the one hand, the Constitutional Court's ruling strengthens protection of debtors' rights and prevents arbitrary action. However, on the other hand, it also creates uncertainty for creditors in securing repayment of financing, particularly because court proceedings are considered time-consuming, costly, and inefficient.

Therefore, a reconstruction of fiduciary guarantee law is needed that can fairly bridge the interests of debtors and creditors. This reconstruction must balance ease of execution for creditors with guarantees of debtors' constitutional rights, and reflect the values of social justice, legal certainty, and human rights protection.

The Conflicting Norms and Legal Consequences of the Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019 in the third and fourth rulings have changed the Fiduciary Guarantee Law and can be considered to have changed the spirit and norms of the fiduciary guarantee institution itself both philosophically, juridically (normatively) and sociologically. Thus, this study attempts to answer these needs by re-exploring the nature of fiduciary guarantees, analyzing legal changes after the Constitutional Court Decision, and formulating a concept for the reconstruction of fiduciary guarantee law that is just in accordance with the philosophy of the Pancasila rule of law.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is classified as a normative-empirical legal research that aims to determine whether the results of the application of law to legal events in concreto are in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations. (Muhaimin, 2020) The approaches used are: statutory approach, normative approach, conceptual approach, historical approach, comparative approach, sociological approach and philosophical approach. Types and sources of data are: primary legal materials, secondary legal materials and tertiary legal materials. This research uses primary data sources as the main data and secondary data as supporting data consisting of primary legal materials and secondary legal materials.

The data collection technique uses a semi-structured in-depth interview method, then the validity of the data is tested using source triangulation, namely comparing the results of interviews from various informants to obtain credible and objective data. All legal materials obtained are then analyzed and processed by building arguments based on logical thinking, also interpreting various legal materials. (Nasution S, 1992) The secondary data that has been obtained is then analyzed qualitatively using deductive reasoning methods as a way to draw conclusions.

DISCUSSION

1. The Essence of Fiduciary Guarantee

a. The Concept of Fiduciary Philosophy

Fiduciary institutions are known by various names or terms. In Roman times, this institution was known as *fiducia-cum-Creditor*. In addition, Asser van Oven also referred to it as Property Rights as Collateral (*Bezitloos zekerheidsrecht*), Kahrel used the expanded term Pawn (*Verruimd Pandbegrip*). Meanwhile, according to A. Veenhoven, it is called "Submission of Property Rights as Collateral (*Eigendomsoverdracht tot Zekerheid*). But ultimately, people prefer to use the shorter term, namely fiduciary, because it is shorter and easier to pronounce." (Hamzah & Manullang, 1987)

The birth of fiduciary institutions arose from practical needs. This need is based on the following facts: (Fuady, 2000)

- 1) Movable property as debt collateral. As is known, according to our legal system, and also the law in most Continental European countries, if the object of debt collateral is movable property, then the collateral is bound in the form of a pledge. In this case, the object of the pledge must be handed over to the party receiving the pledge (creditor). Conversely, if the object of the debt collateral is movable property, then the collateral must be in the form of a mortgage (now there is a mortgage). In this case, the object of the collateral is not handed over to the creditor, but remains in the power of the debtor. However, there are cases where the object of debt collateral is still classified as movable property, but the debtor is reluctant to hand over control over the goods to the creditor, while the creditor has no interest or even inconvenience if the goods are handed over to him. Therefore, there is a need for a form of debt collateral whose object is still classified as movable property but without handing over control over the object to the creditor. Finally, a new form of collateral emerged where the object is movable property, but control over the object does not transfer from the debtor to the creditor. This is what is known as fiduciary security. Conversely, there are also cases where debt security is granted over immovable property, but there is a need, or the parties agree, for the immovable property to be transferred to the creditor. This is what gives rise to the "land mortgage," which is widely practiced in customary law systems.
- 2) Special collateral for debt. There are items that are actually movable but possess the characteristics of immovable property. Therefore, securing them with a pledge is considered insufficient, especially because of the obligation to transfer control of the collateral.

Therefore, fiduciary security is an option. For example, fiduciary security over aircraft existed before the enactment of Law No. 15 of 1992 concerning Aviation. Under this law, a mortgage can be secured over an aircraft. Or over crops, which also cannot be secured by a mortgage.

- 3) The development of new legal institutions of ownership. Developments in ownership of certain objects have not always been accompanied by developments in collateral law, so that some rights to immovable objects cannot be secured by mortgages. For example, strata title or condominiums cannot be secured by mortgages. Therefore, Law No. 16 of 1985 concerning Condominiums introduced fiduciary rights to these condominium units. However, with the enactment of Law No. 4 of 1996 on Mortgage Rights, strata title can be secured by mortgage rights provided certain conditions are met.
- 4) Movable assets that are collateral for a debt cannot be surrendered. Sometimes, both the creditor and the debtor have no objection to having the debt secured by a pledge, but for some reason or another, ownership of the pledged assets cannot be transferred to the creditor. For example, company shares whose certificates have not yet been issued. Therefore, a share fiduciary obligation arises. Or, a fiduciary obligation exists for movable assets, but for some reason or another, the assets are still in the hands of a third party, so that delivery cannot be made. Therefore, a pledge cannot be carried out.

The background to the birth of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law was due to practical needs, these needs can be seen from the following facts: (Fuady, 2000)

- 1) Movable property as collateral for debt. As is known, according to our legal system, and also the law in most Continental European countries, if the object of debt collateral is movable property, then the collateral is bound in the form of a pledge. In this case, the object of the pledge must be handed over to the party receiving the pledge (the creditor). Conversely, if the object of debt collateral is immovable property, then the collateral must take the form of a mortgage (now there is a mortgage). In this case, the object of the collateral is not handed over to the creditor, but remains in the debtor's control. However, there are cases where the object of debt collateral is still movable property, but the debtor is reluctant to hand over control over the object to the creditor, while the creditor has no interest, or even inconvenienced if the object is handed over to him. Therefore, a form of debt collateral is needed that still classifies the object as movable property but does not transfer control over the object to the creditor. Finally, a new form of collateral emerged where the object is movable property, but control over the object does not transfer from the debtor to the creditor.
- 2) Not All Land Rights Can Be Mortgaged. Another factor driving the emergence or development of fiduciary practices is the existence of certain land rights that cannot be secured by mortgages or security interests.
- 3) Collateral for Civil Debts. Some items are actually movable but possess the characteristics of immovable property, making a pledge insufficient, particularly due to the obligation to transfer control of the collateral. Fiduciary collateral is therefore an option.

- 4) The Development of New Legal Institutions of Ownership. The development of ownership of certain goods cannot always be accompanied by the development of collateral, so that the rights to the goods are actually immovable, but cannot be tied to a mortgage.
- 5) Movable Assets That Are the Object of Debt Collateral Cannot Be Transferred. There are times when both the creditor and the debtor do not object to having the debt collateralized in the form of a pledge for the debt they have made, but the collateralized goods for one reason or another cannot be transferred to the creditor.

In addition to the above facts, the background to the birth of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law based on the current situation stated in its considerations is: The very large and increasing need for the business world for the availability of funds, needs to be balanced with the existence of clear and complete legal provisions governing guarantee institutions. The regulation of fiduciary guarantee institutions is still based on jurisprudence. In order to provide legal certainty of legal protection for interested parties.

Article 1 number 1 of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law provides the following limitations and definitions "Fiduciary is the transfer of ownership rights of an object on the basis of trust with the provision that the object whose ownership rights are transferred remains in the possession of the owner of the object."

According to the Regulation of the Chief of Police Number 8 of 2011 concerning the execution of Fiduciary Guarantees, it is stated that Fiduciary is the transfer of ownership rights of an object on the basis of trust with the provision that the object whose ownership rights are transferred remains in the possession of the owner of the object.

b. Philosophical Basis of Fiduciary Guarantee Institutions

Understanding the meaning of legal benefits and functions is essentially an examination of the significance of a legal regulation. Law, accepted as a modern concept, functions to bring about social change. In carrying out its function, law constantly confronts established values and behavioral patterns within society. Guarantee institutions are a necessity for the community of economic actors and business actors. Trust is the basis for agreements, and agreements are strengthened by more concrete guarantees. According to Sri Radjeki Hartono (Hartono, 2007):

"Guarantees as a legal institution give rise to legal principles regulated in civil law which have an important position in economic law."

The collateral institution in the form of a pawn regulated in Book II of the Civil Code is felt to not meet the needs of the community, especially small entrepreneurs, considering the provisions in Article 1152 paragraph (2) of the Civil Code, which requires that: "Tangible movable objects given as collateral in the form of a pawn must move and be in the control of the creditor (inbezit stelling), while the goods as collateral objects are still needed by the debtor to run his business".

To overcome the provisions of Article 1152 paragraph 2 of the Civil Code and meet the community's need for collateral institutions, the Fiduciary Guarantee Law was born. In Article 1 number 1 of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law it is stated that: "Fiduciary is the transfer of

ownership rights of an object on the basis of trust with the provision that the object whose ownership rights are transferred remains in the control of the owner of the object". The rules regarding Fiduciary Guarantee in economic law because fiduciary guarantees are utilized in economic activities, for several reasons including practicality and security.

This guarantee is collateral for debt repayment, which gives the fiduciary holder a primary position over other creditors as regulated in the Fiduciary Guarantee Law. Fiduciary guarantees, viewed from a legal aspect, provide preference (the right to priority repayment) over other (concurrent) creditors as follows: (Salindeho, 1994)

- 1) Fiduciary holders have priority rights over other creditors;
- 2) The Fiduciary Holder has priority rights in terms of taking payment of his receivables from the results of the execution of the object which is the object of the fiduciary guarantee;
- 3) Fiduciary holders have priority rights that are not removed due to bankruptcy and/or liquidation (vide Article 27 UUFJ).

Until now, in the era of multidimensional globalization, including in the world of national and international trade, clear legal regulations regarding Fiduciary remain relevant, because among other things, they will be related to the Global Competitiveness Index (World Competitiveness Index, World Economic Forum), which among several parameters relates to legal issues such as: (Muladi, 2019)

- a. Property Rights;
- b. Judicial Independence;
- c. Burden of Government regulations;
- d. Corporate Ethics;
- e. Financial Market Sophistication;
- f. Ease of Access to Loans;
- g. Efficiency in Legal Framework

Fiduciary institutions are known by various names or terms. In Roman times, this institution was known as *fiducia cum creditore*. Furthermore, Asser van Oven also referred to it as Property Rights as Collateral (*Bezitloos zekerheidsrecht*), while Kahrel used the expanded term Pawn (*Verruimd Pandbegrip*).

Meanwhile, Dr. A. Veenhoven referred to it as Transfer of Property Rights as Collateral (*Eigendomsoverdracht tot Zekerheid*). However, ultimately, people prefer the shorter term, namely fiduciary, because it is shorter and easier to pronounce. (Hamzah & Manullang, 1987)

In the Fiduciary Guarantee Law, when analyzed from an ethical perspective, it is formally and substantively fulfilled, and the legal objective has been achieved, as the positions of debtors and creditors have been met and justice has been achieved. However, in its implementation, determining the measure of justice is very difficult, especially when the debtor is in default.

When analyzed from a utilitarian perspective, the Fiduciary Guarantee Law offers both debtors and creditors the hope of benefit. Debtors will utilize the funds provided by creditors to continue operating their businesses, even increasing productivity and promoting the well-being of the community. Creditors will experience smooth credit payments, allowing their receivables to be quickly repaid and distributed to other debtors.

If analyzed based on dogmatic flow, the Fiduciary Guarantee Law can formally guarantee legal certainty, in accordance with the considerations in letter c, that to fulfill legal needs that can further spur national development and to guarantee legal certainty and be able to provide legal protection for interested parties, it is necessary to form complete provisions regarding fiduciary guarantees and these guarantees need to be registered at the fiduciary registration office.

In substance, the Fiduciary Guarantee Law articles are contrary to the principles of property law, namely the principle of *droit de suite*, objects move following their owners, and mix up the principle of ownership of objects (*eigenaar*) with the principle of control of objects (*bezitter*).

2. Implementation of Fiduciary Guarantees Before and After the Constitutional Court Decision

a. Arrangement Execution Fiduciary Guarantee According to Law No. 49 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantee (Before Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019)

Based on Article 11 of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees, objects used as fiduciary guarantees are required to be registered at the fiduciary registration office at the office. Ministry Law and Human Rights. The registration application is carried out by the creditor/recipient of the fiduciary guarantee (according to Article 13 Paragraph (1) of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law), and if after registration is carried out, the fiduciary registration office issues a guarantee certificate. The same fiduciary as the date of receipt of the fiduciary application.

In the certificate Fiduciary guarantees contain a decree that reads "For the Sake of Justice Based on the Almighty God", then the fiduciary guarantee certificate has the same executorial power as a court decision that has permanent legal force.

Based on Article 15 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees, if the creditor/recipient of the fiduciary guarantee does not register the fiduciary registration guarantee at the fiduciary registration office, then the fiduciary guarantee does not have executorial power and cannot be executed by force through the court if the debtor cannot fulfill his performance/breach of promise.

The Process of Executing Fiduciary Guarantees according to Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees.

Article 29 of Law Number 42 of 1999 regulates 3 (three) methods of executing fiduciary collateral, including the following:

- 1) The implementation of the executorial title as regulated in Article 15 paragraph (2) by the fiduciary recipient in this case is the creditor. The article reads "The Fiduciary Guarantee Certificate as referred to in paragraph (1) has the same executorial power as a court decision that has obtained permanent legal force." In the fiduciary guarantee certificate issued by the Fiduciary Guarantee Registration Office, the words "For the Sake of Justice Based on the One Almighty God" are included, so this fiduciary guarantee certificate has the same executorial power as a court decision that has permanent legal force.
- 2) The sale of fiduciary collateral objects is carried out under the authority of the fiduciary recipient through a public auction. This type of sale is known as parate execution and requires a public sale (auction). Therefore, parate execution is the authority granted by law or a court decision to one party to enforce the terms of an agreement if the debtor fails to fulfill its obligations (default). Therefore, if the debtor fails to fulfill its obligations (default), the financial institution can sell the fiduciary collateral objects through a public auction to obtain repayment of the debt.
- 3) Underhand sales are carried out based on an agreement between the fiduciary giver and recipient if in this way the highest price can be obtained that is profitable for both parties. This mechanism can be carried out after the lapse of 1 (one) month since written notification by the fiduciary giver and recipient to the interested parties and announced in at least 2 (two) newspapers circulating in the relevant area. So in principle the implementation of underhand sales is carried out by the fiduciary giver/debtor himself, then the proceeds of the sale are handed over to the fiduciary recipient/creditor to pay off the debt of the fiduciary giver (debtor). Implementation of Fiduciary Guarantee Execution According to Regulation of the Chief of the Indonesian National Police No. 8 of 2011 Concerning the Security of Fiduciary Guarantee Execution

b. Regulations on the Execution of Fiduciary Guarantees Following Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019

On January 6, 2020, the Constitutional Court Panel of Judges issued a decision on the material review case against Article 15 Paragraph (2) and Paragraph (3) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees. This case began when the debtor/fiduciary guarantee provider had entered into a multi-purpose financing agreement with the creditor/fiduciary guarantee recipient for the provision of funds for the purchase of one car unit in accordance with the agreement agreed upon between the parties, the debtor is obliged to pay the debt to the creditor with the nominal amount agreed upon in the agreement within a period of 35 months. However, in the middle of the agreement, the creditor/fiduciary guarantee recipient sent his representative, a debt collector, to take the debtor's vehicle with arbitrary actions without going through the correct legal procedures. Regarding the arbitrary actions carried out by the debt collector, the South Jakarta District Court Judge with case register 345/PDT.G/2018/PN.Jkt.Sel decided that the creditor/fiduciary guarantee recipient and the debt collector were declared to have committed an unlawful act and sentenced the creditor/fiduciary guarantee recipient and the debt collector jointly and severally to pay material and immaterial losses to the debtor/fiduciary guarantee provider.

However, the creditor/fiduciary guarantee recipient did not implement the decision of the South Jakarta District Court by again forcibly repossessing the debtor/fiduciary guarantee provider's vehicle in the presence of the police. Based on this action, the debtor/fiduciary guarantee provider finally filed a request for material review to the Constitutional Court with the argument that Article 15 paragraph (2) and Article 15 paragraph (3) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees are contrary to the 1945 Constitution, especially Article 1 Paragraph (3), Article 27 Paragraph (1), Article 28D Paragraph (1), Article 28G Paragraph (1), and Article 28H Paragraph (4). Regarding the request for a material review of Article 15 Paragraph (2) and Paragraph (3) of Law No. 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees, the implementation of the rights of creditors/fiduciary guarantee recipients has changed in line with the Decision of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number: 18/PUU-XVII/2019 on January 6, 2020. In its decision, the Constitutional Court stated the following:

- 1) Declaring Article 15 paragraph (2) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 1999 Number 168, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3889) insofar as the phrase "executory power" and the phrase "equal to a court decision that has permanent legal force" is contrary to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and does not have binding legal force insofar as it is not interpreted as "with regard to fiduciary guarantees where there is no agreement regarding breach of promise (default) and the debtor objects to voluntarily hand over the object that is the fiduciary guarantee, then all legal mechanisms and procedures in implementing the execution of the guarantee certificate must be carried out and apply the same as implementing the execution of a court decision that has permanent legal force.

- 2) Declaring Article 15 Paragraph (3) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 1999 Number 168, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3889) insofar as the phrase "breach of promise" is contrary to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and does not have binding legal force insofar as it is not interpreted to mean that "the existence of a breach of promise is not determined unilaterally by the creditor but rather on the basis of an agreement between the creditor and the debtor or on the basis of legal remedies that determine that a breach of promise has occurred."
- 3) Declaring the Explanation of Article 15 Paragraph (2) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 1999 Number 168, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3889) insofar as the phrase "executory power" is contrary to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and does not have binding legal force as long as it is not interpreted as "with regard to fiduciary guarantees where there is no agreement regarding breach of promise and the debtor objects to voluntarily hand over the object that is the fiduciary guarantee, then all legal mechanisms and procedures in implementing the execution of the fiduciary guarantee certificate must be carried out and apply the same as implementing the execution of a court decision that has permanent legal force."

Based on the Constitutional Court's decision, a breach of promise determined unilaterally by the creditor and not based on an agreement between the two parties results in the execution of the fiduciary guarantee not being able to be carried out directly by the fiduciary recipient (creditor) but must submit an application to the District Court. Therefore, the execution parate after the Constitutional Court's decision can still be implemented as long as there is an agreement between the debtor and creditor and the debtor surrenders the object of execution voluntarily. In addition, the Constitutional Court also believes that even though the request for material review is requested to test the provisions of Article 15 paragraph (2) of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law, after the phrase "executory power" and the phrase "equal to a court decision that has permanent legal force" and the phrase "breach of promise" in Article 15 paragraph (3) of Law Number 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees were declared unconstitutional.

The Constitutional Court stated that the Explanation of Article 15 paragraph (2) of the Fiduciary Guarantee Law, the phrase "executory power" is contrary to the 1945 Constitution and does not have binding legal force as long as it is not interpreted as "with regard to fiduciary guarantees where there is no agreement regarding breach of promise and the debtor objects to voluntarily hand over the object that is the fiduciary guarantee, then all legal mechanisms and procedures in implementing the execution of the fiduciary guarantee certificate must be implemented and apply the same as the execution of a court decision that has permanent legal force.

Following Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019, fiduciary guarantee recipients or creditors cannot execute the guarantee themselves (parate execution) but must submit a request for execution to the District Court. Parate execution can be implemented if there is an agreement regarding the breach of promise stipulated at the outset of the agreement

and the debtor is willing to voluntarily surrender the fiduciary guarantee object. The Constitutional Court ruling states that not all executions of fiduciary collateral must be conducted through the courts. In cases where there is no agreement regarding breach of contract between the creditor and the debtor, and the debtor objects to voluntarily surrendering the fiduciary collateral, all legal mechanisms and procedures for enforcing the fiduciary collateral must be implemented and apply in the same manner as a legally binding court decision.

If the agreement does not contain agreed-upon criteria for breach of contract between the debtor and creditor, and the debtor is reluctant to voluntarily hand over the fiduciary collateral to the creditor, the court becomes the arbitrator who grants permission for execution if the conditions have been met. Not all withdrawals of collateral can be carried out through the courts, because this can result in the courts experiencing a backlog in handling cases for the execution of fiduciary collateral objects, in addition to many other cases that must also be resolved through the courts. As explained above, after the Constitutional Court's decision, the recipient of fiduciary rights/creditor can no longer carry out parate execution but must submit an application for execution to the District Court. The Constitutional Court ruling states that not all executions of fiduciary collateral must be carried out through the courts; however, parate execution may also be carried out. The fiduciary agreement clause does not regulate a clause regarding a default agreement between the creditor and the debtor. If the debtor objects to voluntarily surrendering the fiduciary collateral, all legal mechanisms and procedures for executing the fiduciary collateral must be implemented and applied in the same manner as a legally binding court decision.

On the other hand, if there is no default agreement criteria in the fiduciary agreement and the debtor is reluctant to provide the collateral object to the creditor, then the execution will be carried out through the District Court. The problem after the Constitutional Court decision Number 18/PUU-XVII/2019 is if when the creditor submits an application for execution of the fiduciary collateral object to the District Court, but before the decision is issued for the execution of the fiduciary collateral, the debtor or the fiduciary guarantor who has bad intentions can intentionally remove the fiduciary collateral object or the debtor changes address so that its existence is not known.

3. Reconstruction Fair Fiduciary Guarantee Law

From the perspective of the theory of legal certainty, the system for forming national legislation requires a clear, non-overlapping institutional structure and firm authority in every stage of regulatory formation, including harmonization and evaluation.

a. The Basis of Reconstruction Thought

Legal reconstruction is part of the legal system renewal process, encompassing not only normative aspects but also philosophical, sociological, and practical aspects. In the context of fiduciary guarantees in Indonesia, the need for reconstruction arises from the imbalance between the protection of creditor and debtor rights, which was glaringly evident in the execution practices prior to Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019. The Constitutional Court's ruling changed the paradigm of fiduciary guarantee enforcement by

emphasizing the importance of default agreements or court decisions. This emphasizes that formal (legalistic) justice is insufficient; the law must favor substantive justice. Therefore, the reconstruction of fiduciary law must be directed at improving: legal norms (revision of legislation), institutional structures (fair and efficient enforcement mechanisms), philosophical values (the principle of balanced trust), and technical aspects (transparency and accountability of the registration system).

b. Reconstruction Proposal

1) Normative Reconstruction: Adjustment of Article 15 of Law No. 42 of 1999 Article 15 paragraphs (2) and (3) provide executorial power to fiduciary guarantee deeds, but this article does not explicitly regulate protection for debtors. Therefore, an amendment is needed which:

- (a) Requires a written agreement regarding default as a condition of execution,
- (b) Requires official notification to the debtor before execution,
- (c) Providing resolution options through non-litigation institutions.

Example of new article formulation:

"Execution of the fiduciary guarantee object can only be carried out after there is a written agreement between the parties regarding the occurrence of default, or based on a court decision that has permanent legal force."

2) Institutional Reconstruction: Establishment of the Fiduciary Guarantee Mediation Institution (LMJF)

- (a) This institution is tasked with:
- (b) Default clarification center,
- (c) Mediation facilitator between creditors and debtors,
- (d) Recommendation for peaceful execution or debt restructuring.
- (e) This institution can be under the supervision of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights and collaborate with the Financial Services Authority (OJK) and judicial institutions to provide execution recommendations without having to go through a lengthy and expensive lawsuit process.

3) Philosophical Reconstruction: Reformulation of the Principles of Belief

The principle of trust in fiduciary law has been interpreted unilaterally as "the creditor trusts the debtor to fulfill his obligations." However, in a just legal system, the meaning of trust needs to be expanded:

- (a) The state places trust as a horizontal and equal relationship between the parties.
- (b) The state is present to monitor and balance the positions of creditors and debtors, not just to give power to creditors.

- (c) This approach is in line with Satjipto Rahardjo's progressive legal theory, which positions law as a means of liberating and protecting the weak in society.
- 4) Technical Reconstruction: Digitalization and Integration of Fiduciary Systems
 - (a) The current fiduciary registration system is still limited to manual or semi-digital recording via the Ministry of Law and Human Rights website. Yet, this registration is key to the validity of execution.
 - (b) Strengthening the blockchain-based digital registration system to ensure data validity and security.
 - (c) Integration of fiduciary data with OJK, BI, Samsat, and the police, so that all parties can access the status of fiduciary objects.
 - (d) Providing limited public access so that third parties know if an item has been used as fiduciary collateral.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

- a. The essence of fiduciary security in the Indonesian legal system is a form of material security based on the principle of trust, where the fiduciary retains physical control over the collateral, while ownership is legally transferred to the fiduciary recipient. Fiduciary security is a crucial instrument in the modern financing system, but its implementation creates tension between the interests of creditors and the protection of debtors' rights.
- b. Prior to Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019, the execution of fiduciary guarantees was carried out unilaterally by creditors through a parate execution mechanism based on Article 15 of Law No. 42 of 1999. This often led to deviations in practice, including violations of debtors' rights. The Constitutional Court Decision corrected this practice and required a default agreement and voluntary surrender, or a request to the court, as a valid condition for the execution.
- c. A just model for reconstructing fiduciary guarantee law must be developed by balancing legal protection for debtors and creditors. This reconstruction includes:
 - 1) Normative revisions to Law No. 42 of 1999 concerning Fiduciary Guarantees, Article 15 of the Fiduciary Law. This revision relates to the preparation of transparent, gradual, and supervised execution procedures, the establishment of a supervisory system for executors (including debt collectors),
 - 2) Establish a special agency/institution/ad hoc body to handle fiduciary problems/disputes
 - 3) Strengthening the blockchain-based digital registration system to ensure data validity and security.

- 4) Integration of fiduciary data with OJK, BI, Samsat, and the police, so that all parties can access the status of fiduciary objects.
- 5) Implementation studies in real cases in NTB show that legal reconstruction is urgently needed to prevent arbitrary actions, maintain legal order, and strengthen the legitimacy of fiduciary implementation in the eyes of the public.

2. Suggestions

The government and law-making institutions need to strengthen the conceptual understanding that fiduciary guarantees are trust-based material guarantees (fiduciary) that emphasize the balance of rights and obligations of the parties. The government needs to officially revise Law No. 42 of 1999 to align with the Constitutional Court's ruling to prevent a legal vacuum and inconsistencies in implementation. Academics, practitioners, and policymakers need to view Constitutional Court Decision No. 18/PUU-XVII/2019 as a transformative milestone, not merely a legal correction, but a starting point for building a guarantee system that is more humane, just, and aligned with constitutional values.

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